

Milestone: M3.3: Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified

Lead Participant: BSC

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Means of Verification

- [M3.3 report](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

no

Project participants & others

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Next action steps

- Capture proposed metrics by executing identified workflows with the proposed datasets, either reference, synthetic or ad-hoc ones
- Compare the proposed metrics with the ones in usegalaxy.eu and propose mechanisms to map their metrics with the ones proposed in STEERS Task 3.3
- Keep interacting with communities to have a more comprehensive and broad list of use-case workflows to facilitate the metrics gathering process

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